

Table SM1. Mean and SE values for density (ind.m⁻²) and biomass (g wet weight m⁻²) of the benthic macrofauna of the continental slope and São Paulo plateau according to depth (m) in Santos Basin, SW Atlantic.

Depth (m)	400		700		1000		1300		1900		2200		2400	
Density (ind.m ⁻²)	mean	SE												
Annelida	4146	642	2029	266	1643	193	1258	187	612	43	292	31	343	25
Crustacea	756	115	560	85	491	68	442	91	164	21	48	5	84	19
Mollusca	501	115	211	85	200	68	78	91	43	21	19	5	33	19
Other	257	29	240	22	153	26	119	16	65	10	18	3	26	5
Biomass (g WW m ⁻²)	mean	SE												
Annelida	1.606	0.404	0.783	0.094	0.658	0.125	0.474	0.083	0.234	0.042	0.106	0.023	0.105	0.014
Crustacea	0.249	0.038	0.128	0.020	0.073	0.013	0.060	0.015	0.029	0.006	0.018	0.009	0.009	0.002
Mollusca	0.392	0.129	0.163	0.033	0.088	0.027	0.055	0.023	0.034	0.005	0.015	0.009	0.026	0.006
Other	0.021	0.003	0.016	0.003	0.012	0.002	0.008	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001